

A Generalized Family Of Estimators For Estimating Population Mean Using Two Auxiliary Attributes

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Abstract

This paper deals with the problem of estimating the finite population mean when some information on two auxiliary attributes are available. A class of estimators is defined which includes the estimators recently proposed by Malik and Singh (2012), Naik and Gupta (1996) and Singh et al. (2007) as particular cases. It is shown that the proposed estimator is more efficient than the usual mean estimator and other existing estimators. The study is also extended to two-phase sampling. The results have been illustrated numerically by taking empirical population considered in the literature.

Keywords Simple random sampling, two-phase sampling, auxiliary attribute, point bi-serial correlation, phi correlation, efficiency.

1. Introduction

There are some situations when in place of one auxiliary attribute, we have information on two qualitative variables. For illustration, to estimate the hourly wages we can use the information on marital status and region of residence (see Gujrati and Sangeetha (2007), page-311). Here we assume that both auxiliary attributes have significant point bi-serial correlation with the study variable and there is significant phi-correlation (see Yule (1912)) between the auxiliary attributes. The use of auxiliary information can increase the precision of an estimator when study variable Y is highly correlated with auxiliary variables X . In survey sampling, auxiliary variables are present in form of ratio scale variables (e.g. income, output, prices, costs, height and temperature) but sometimes may present in the form of qualitative or nominal scale such as sex, race, color, religion, nationality and geographical region. For example, female workers are found to earn less than their male counterparts do or non-white workers are found to earn less than whites (see Gujrati and Sangeetha (2007), page 304). Naik and Gupta (1996) introduced a ratio estimator when the study variable and the auxiliary attribute are positively correlated. Jhaji et al. (2006) suggested a family of estimators for the population mean in single and two-phase sampling when the study variable

and auxiliary attribute are positively correlated. Shabbir and Gupta (2007), Singh et al. (2008), Singh et al. (2010) and Abd-Elfattah et al. (2010) have considered the problem of estimating population mean $\bar{Y}$ taking into consideration the point biserial correlation between auxiliary attribute and study variable.

2. Some Estimators in Literature

In order to have an estimate of the study variable y , assuming the knowledge of the population proportion P , Naik and Gupta (1996) and Singh et al. (2007) respectively, proposed following estimators:

$$t_1 = \bar{y} \left(\frac{P_1}{p_1} \right) \quad (2.1)$$

$$t_2 = \bar{y} \left(\frac{P_2}{P_2} \right) \quad (2.2)$$

$$t_3 = \bar{y} \exp \left(\frac{P_1 - p_1}{P_1 + p_1} \right) \quad (2.3)$$

$$t_4 = \bar{y} \exp \left(\frac{p_2 - P_2}{p_2 + P_2} \right) \quad (2.4)$$

The Bias and MSE expression's of the estimator's t_i ($i=1, 2, 3, 4$) up to the first order of approximation are, respectively, given by

$$B(t_1) = \bar{Y} f_1 C_{p_1}^2 [1 - K_{pb_1}] \quad (2.5)$$

$$B(t_2) = \bar{Y} f_1 K_{pb_2} C_{p_2}^2 \quad (2.6)$$

$$B(t_3) = \bar{Y} f_1 \frac{C_{p_2}^2}{2} \left[\frac{1}{4} - K_{pb_2} \right] \quad (2.7)$$

$$B(t_4) = \bar{Y} f_1 \frac{C_{p_2}^2}{2} \left[\frac{1}{4} + K_{pb_2} \right] \quad (2.8)$$

$$MSE(t_1) = \bar{Y}^2 f_1 [C_y^2 + C_{p_1}^2 (1 - 2K_{pb_1})] \quad (2.9)$$

$$MSE(t_2) = \bar{Y}^2 f_1 [C_y^2 + C_{p_1}^2 (1 + 2K_{pb_2})] \quad (2.10)$$

$$\text{MSE}(t_3) = \bar{Y}^2 f_1 \left[C_y^2 + C_{p_1}^2 \left(\frac{1}{4} - K_{pb_2} \right) \right] \quad (2.11)$$

$$\text{MSE}(t_4) = \bar{Y}^2 f_1 \left[C_y^2 + C_{p_2}^2 \left(\frac{1}{4} + K_{pb_2} \right) \right] \quad (2.12)$$

where, $f_1 = \frac{1}{n} - \frac{1}{N}$, $S_{\phi_j}^2 = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (\phi_{ji} - P_j)^2$, $S_{y\phi_j} = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{Y})(\phi_{ji} - P_j)$,

$$\rho_{pb_j} = \frac{S_{y\phi_j}}{S_y S_{\phi_j}}, \quad C_y = \frac{S_y}{\bar{Y}}, \quad C_{p_j} = \frac{S_{\phi_j}}{P_j}; \quad (j=1,2),$$

$$K_{pb_1} = \rho_{pb_1} \frac{C_y}{C_{p_1}}, \quad K_{pb_2} = \rho_{pb_2} \frac{C_y}{C_{p_2}}.$$

$s_{\phi_1\phi_2} = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (\phi_{1i} - p_1)(\phi_{2i} - p_2)$ and $\rho_\phi = \frac{S_{\phi_1\phi_2}}{S_{\phi_1} S_{\phi_2}}$ be the sample phi-covariance and phi-

correlation between ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 respectively, corresponding to the population phi-covariance

and phi-correlation $S_{\phi_1\phi_2} = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (\phi_{1i} - P_1)(\phi_{2i} - P_2)$

and $\rho_\phi = \frac{S_{\phi_1\phi_2}}{S_{\phi_1} S_{\phi_2}}$.

Malik and Singh (2012) proposed estimators t_5 and t_6 as

$$t_5 = \bar{y} \left(\frac{P_1}{p_1} \right)^{\alpha_1} \left(\frac{P_2}{p_2} \right)^{\alpha_2} \quad (2.13)$$

$$t_6 = \bar{y} \exp \left(\frac{P_1 - p_1}{P_1 + p_1} \right)^{\beta_1} \exp \left(\frac{p_2 - P_2}{p_2 + P_2} \right)^{\beta_2} \quad (2.14)$$

where $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1$ and β_2 are real constants.

The Bias and MSE expression's of the estimator's t_5 and t_6 up to the first order of approximation are, respectively, given by

$$\text{B}(t_5) = \bar{Y} f_1 \left(C_{p_1}^2 \left[\frac{\alpha_1^2}{2} + \frac{\alpha_1}{2} - \alpha_1 K_{pb_1} \right] + C_{p_2}^2 \left[\frac{\alpha_2^2}{2} + \frac{\alpha_2}{2} - \alpha_2 K_{pb_2} + \alpha_1 \alpha_2 K_\phi \right] \right) \quad (2.15)$$

$$B(t_6) = \bar{Y}f_1 \left[C_{p_1}^2 \left(\frac{\beta_1^2}{4} - \frac{\beta_1}{2} K_{pb_1} \right) + C_{p_2}^2 \left(\frac{\beta_2^2}{4} + \frac{\beta_2}{2} K_{pb_2} - \frac{\beta_1\beta_2}{4} K_\phi \right) \right] \quad (2.16)$$

$$MSE(t_5) = \bar{Y}^2 f_1 \left[C_y^2 + C_{p_1}^2 (\alpha_1^2 - 2\alpha_1 K_{pb_1}) + C_{p_2}^2 (\alpha_2^2 - 2\alpha_2 K_{pb_2} + 2\alpha_1\alpha_2 K_\phi) \right] \quad (2.17)$$

$$MSE(t_6) = \bar{Y}^2 f_1 \left[C_y^2 + C_{p_1}^2 \left(\frac{\beta_1^2}{4} - \beta_1 K_{pb_1} \right) + C_{p_2}^2 \left(\frac{\beta_2^2}{4} - \frac{\beta_1\beta_2}{2} K_\phi + \beta_2 K_{pb_1} \right) \right] \quad (2.18)$$

3. The Suggested Class of Estimators

Using linear combination of t_i ($i=0,1,2$), we define an estimator of the form

$$t_p = \sum_{i=0}^3 w_i t_i \in H \quad (3.1)$$

$$\text{Such that, } \sum_{i=0}^3 w_i = 1 \quad \text{and } w_i \in R \quad (3.2)$$

Where,

$$t_0 = \bar{y}, \quad t_1 = \bar{y} \left[\frac{L_1 P_1 + L_2}{L_1 p_1 + L_2} \right]^{\alpha_1} \left[\frac{L_3 P_2 + L_4}{L_3 p_2 + L_4} \right]^{\alpha_2}$$

and $t_2 = \exp \left[\frac{(L_5 P_1 + L_6) - (L p_1 + L_6)}{(L_1 P_1 + L_2) + (L_5 p_1 + L_6)} \right]^{\beta_1} \exp \left[\frac{(L_7 p_2 + L_6) - (L_7 P_2 + L_8)}{(L_7 p_2 + L_2) + (L_7 P_2 + L_8)} \right]^{\beta_2}$

where w_i ($i=0,1,2$) denotes the constants used for reducing the bias in the class of estimators, H denotes the set of those estimators that can be constructed from t_i ($i=0,1,2$) and R denotes the set of real numbers (for detail see Singh et. al (2008)). Also, L_i ($i=1,2,\dots,8$) are either real numbers or the functions of the known parameters of the auxiliary attributes.

Expressing t_p in terms of e 's, we have

$$t_p = \bar{Y}(1+e_0) \left[\begin{array}{l} w_0 + w_1 (1+\varphi_1 e_1)^{-\alpha_1} (1+\varphi_2 e_2)^{-\alpha_2} \\ + w_2 \exp(-\theta_1 e_1 [1+\theta_1 e_1]^{-1})^{\beta_1} \\ \exp(-\theta_2 e_2 [1+\theta_2 e_2]^{-1})^{\beta_2} \end{array} \right] \quad (3.3)$$

where,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \varphi_1 &= \frac{L_1 P_1}{L_1 P_1 + L_2} \\ \varphi_2 &= \frac{L_3 P_2}{L_3 P_1 + L_4} \\ \theta_1 &= \frac{L_5 P_1}{2[L_5 P_2 + L_6]} \\ \theta_2 &= \frac{L_7 P_2}{2[L_7 P_2 + L_8]} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

After expanding, Subtracting $\bar{Y}$ from both sides of the equation (3.3) and neglecting the term having power greater than two, we have

$$(t_p - \bar{Y}) = \bar{Y} [e_0 - w_1(\alpha_1 \varphi_1 e_1 + \alpha_2 \varphi_2 e_2) - w_2(\beta_1 \theta_1 e_1 - \beta_2 \theta_2 e_2)] \quad (3.4)$$

Squaring both sides of (3.4) and then taking expectations, we get MSE of the estimator t_p up to the first order of approximation, as

$$\text{MSE}(t_p) = \bar{Y}^2 [w_1^2 T_1 + w_2^2 T_2 + 2w_1 w_2 T_3 - 2w_1 T_4 - 2w_2 T_5] \quad (3.5)$$

where,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} w_1 &= \frac{L_2 L_4 - L_3 L_5}{L_1 L_2 - L_3^2} \\ w_2 &= \frac{L_1 L_5 - L_3 L_4}{L_1 L_2 - L_3^2} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3.6)$$

and

$$\left. \begin{aligned} L_1 &= \varphi_1^2 \alpha_1^2 C_{p_1}^2 + \varphi_2^2 \alpha_2^2 C_{p_2}^2 + 2\alpha_1 \alpha_2 \varphi_1 \varphi_2 k_\varphi C_{p_2}^2 \\ L_2 &= \theta_1^2 \beta_1^2 C_{p_1}^2 + \theta_2^2 \beta_2^2 C_{p_1}^2 - 2\beta_1 \beta_2 \varphi_1 \theta_2 k_\varphi C_{p_2}^2 \\ L_3 &= \alpha_1 \beta_1 \theta_1 C_{p_1}^2 - \alpha_2 \beta_2 \theta_2 C_{p_2}^2 + \alpha_2 \beta_1 \varphi_2 \theta_1 k_\varphi C_{p_2}^2 - \alpha_1 \varphi_1 \theta_2 \beta_2 k_\varphi C_{p_2}^2 \\ L_4 &= \alpha_1 \varphi_1 k_{pb_1} C_{p_1}^2 + \alpha_2 \varphi_2 k_{pb_2} C_{p_2}^2 \\ L_5 &= \beta_1 \theta_1 k_{pb_1} C_{p_1}^2 - \beta_2 \theta_2 k_{pb_2} C_{p_2}^2 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3.7)$$

4. Empirical Study

Data: (Source: Government of Pakistan (2004))

The population consists rice cultivation areas in 73 districts of Pakistan. The variables are defined as:

Y = rice production (in 000' tonnes, with one tonne = 0.984 ton) during 2003,

P_1 = production of farms where rice production is more than 20 tonnes during the year 2002, and

P_2 = proportion of farms with rice cultivation area more than 20 ha during the year 2003.

For this data, we have

$N=73, \bar{Y}=61.3, P_1=0.4247, P_2=0.3425, S_y^2=12371.4, S_{\phi_1}^2=0.225490, S_{\phi_2}^2=0.228311,$

$\rho_{pb_1}=0.621, \rho_{pb_2}=0.673, \rho_\phi=0.889.$

Table 4.1: PRE of different estimators of $\bar{Y}$ with respect to $\bar{y}$.

CHOICE OF SCALERS, when $w_0 = 0 \ w_1 = 1 \ w_2 = 0$						
α_1	α_2	L_1	L_2	L_3	L_4	PRE'S
0	1			1	0	179.77
1	0	1	0			162.68
1	1	1	1	1	1	156.28
-1	1	1	0	1	0	112.97
1	1	C_{P_1}	ρ_{pb_1}	C_{P_2}	ρ_{pb_2}	178.10
1	1	NP_1	K_{pb_1}	NP_2	K_{pb_2}	110.95
-1	1	NP_1	f	NP_2	f	112.78
-1	1	N	K_{pb_1}	N	K_{pb_2}	112.68
-1	1	NP_1	P_1	NP_2	P_2	112.32
1	1	n	P_1	n	P_2	115.32
-1	1	N	ρ_{pb_1}	N	ρ_{pb_2}	112.38
-1	1	n	P_1	n	P_2	113.00
-1	1	N	P_1	N	P_2	112.94
When, $w_0 = 0 \ w_1 = 0 \ w_2 = 1$						

β_1	β_2	L_5	L_6	L_7	L_8	PRE'S
1	0	1	0	1	0	141.81
0	1	1	0	1	0	60.05
1	-1	1	0	1	0	180.50
1	-1	1	1	1	1	127.39
1	-1	1	1	1	0	170.59
1	-1	C_{p_1}	ρ_{pb_1}	C_{p_2}	ρ_{pb_2}	143.83
1	-1	NP_1	K_{pb_1}	NP_2	K_{pb_2}	179.95
1	-1	NP_1	f	NP_2	f	180.52
1	-1	N	K_{pb_1}	N	K_{pb_2}	180.56
1	-1	NP_1	P_1	NP_2	P_2	180.53
1	-1	n	P_1	n	P_2	179.49
1	-1	N	ρ_{pb_1}	N	ρ_{pb_2}	180.55
1	-1	n	P_1	n	P_2	180.36
1	-1	N	P_1	N	P_2	180.57
When, $w_0 = 0$ $w_1 = 0$ $w_2 = 1$ also $L_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, 8) = 1$ $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = \beta_1 = \beta_2 = 1$ PRE(t_p) = 183.60						

5. Double Sampling

It is assumed that the population proportion P_1 for the first auxiliary attribute ϕ_1 is unknown but the same is known for the second auxiliary attribute ϕ_2 . When P_1 is unknown, it is some times estimated from a preliminary large sample of size n' on which only the attribute ϕ_1 is measured. Then a second phase sample of size n ($n < n'$) is drawn and Y is observed.

Let $p'_j = \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{i=1}^{n'} \phi_{ji}, (j = 1, 2).$

The estimator's t_1, t_2, t_3 and t_4 in two-phase sampling take the following form

$$t_{d1} = \bar{y} \left(\frac{p'_1}{p_1} \right) \tag{5.1}$$

$$t_{d2} = \bar{y} \left(\frac{P_2}{p_2} \right) \quad (5.2)$$

$$t_{d3} = \bar{y} \exp \left(\frac{p_1' - p_1}{p_1 + p_1} \right) \quad (5.3)$$

$$t_{d4} = \bar{y} \exp \left(\frac{p_2' - P_2}{p_2 + P_2} \right) \quad (5.4)$$

The bias and MSE expressions of the estimators t_{d1} , t_{d2} , t_{d3} and t_{d4} up to first order of approximation, are respectively given as

$$B(t_{d1}) = \bar{Y} f_3 C_{p_1}^2 [1 - k_{pb_1}] \quad (5.5)$$

$$B(t_{d2}) = \bar{Y} f_2 C_{p_2}^2 [1 - K_{pb_2}] \quad (5.6)$$

$$B(t_{d3}) = \bar{Y} f_3 \frac{C_{p_2}^2}{4} [1 - K_{pb_2}] \quad (5.7)$$

$$B(t_{d4}) = \bar{Y} f_3 \frac{C_{p_2}^2}{4} [1 + K_{pb_2}] \quad (5.8)$$

$$MSE(t_{d1}) = \bar{Y}^2 [f_1 C_y^2 + f_3 C_{p_1}^2 (1 - 2K_{pb_1})] \quad (5.9)$$

$$MSE(t_{d2}) = \bar{Y}^2 [f_1 C_y^2 + f_2 C_{p_2}^2 (1 - 2K_{pb_2})] \quad (5.10)$$

$$MSE(t_{d3}) = \bar{Y}^2 \left[f_1 C_y^2 + f_3 \frac{C_{p_1}^2}{4} (1 - 4K_{pb_1}) \right] \quad (5.11)$$

$$MSE(t_{d4}) = \bar{Y}^2 \left[f_1 C_y^2 + f_3 \frac{C_{p_1}^2}{4} (1 + 4K_{pb_1}) \right] \quad (5.12)$$

where,

$$S_{\phi_j}^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (\phi_{ji} - p_j)^2, \quad S_{\phi_j'}^2 = \frac{1}{n'-1} \sum_{i=1}^{n'} (\phi_{ji}' - p_j')^2,$$

$$f_2 = \frac{1}{n'} - \frac{1}{N}, \quad f_3 = \frac{1}{n} - \frac{1}{n'}.$$

The estimator's t_5 and t_6 , in two-phase sampling, takes the following form

$$t_{d5} = \bar{y} \left(\frac{p_1}{P_1} \right)^{m_1} \left(\frac{P_2}{p_2} \right)^{m_2} \quad (5.13)$$

$$t_{d6} = \bar{y} \exp \left(\frac{p_1 - P_1}{p_1 + P_1} \right)^{n_1} \exp \left(\frac{P_2 - p_2}{p_2 + P_2} \right)^{n_2} \quad (5.14)$$

Where m_1, m_2, n_1 and n_2 are real constants.

The Bias and MSE expression's of the estimator's t_{d5} and t_{d6} up to the first order of approximation are, respectively, given by

$$B(t_{d5}) = \bar{Y} \left[f_3 C_{p_1}^2 \left(\frac{m_1^2}{2} + \frac{m_1}{2} - m_1 K_{pb_1} \right) + f_2 C_{P_2}^2 \left(\frac{m_2^2}{2} + \frac{m_2}{2} - m_2 k_{pb_2} \right) \right] \quad (5.15)$$

$$B(t_{d6}) = \bar{Y} \left[f_3 \left(\frac{n_1^2}{8} + \frac{n_1}{8} - \frac{n_1}{2} K_{pb_1} \right) C_{p_1}^2 + f_2 \left(\frac{n_2^2}{8} + \frac{n_2}{8} + \frac{n_2}{2} K_{pb_2} \right) \right] \quad (5.16)$$

$$MSE(t_{d5}) = \bar{Y} \left[f_1 C_y^2 + f_3 C_{p_1}^2 (m_1^2 - 2m_1 K_{pb_1}) + f_2 C_{P_2}^2 (m_2^2 - 2m_2 K_{pb_2}) \right] \quad (5.17)$$

$$MSE(t_{d6}) = \bar{Y}^2 \left[f_1 C_y^2 + f_3 \left(\frac{n_1^2}{4} - n_1 K_{pb_1} \right) C_{p_1}^2 + f_2 \left(\frac{n_2^2}{4} + n_2 K_{pb_2} \right) C_{P_2}^2 \right] \quad (5.18)$$

6. Estimator t_{pd} in Two-Phase Sampling

Using linear combination of t_{di} ($i = 0, 1, 2$), we define an estimator of the form

$$t_{pd} = \sum_{i=0}^3 h_i t_{di} \in H \quad (6.1)$$

$$\text{Such that, } \sum_{i=0}^3 h_i = 1 \quad \text{and } h_i \in \mathbf{R} \quad (6.2)$$

where,

$$t_0 = \bar{y}, \quad t_{d1} = \bar{y} \left[\frac{L_1 p'_1 + L_2}{L_1 p_1 + L_2} \right]^{m_1} \left[\frac{L_3 P_2 + L_4}{L_3 p'_2 + L_4} \right]^{m_2}$$

$$\text{and } t_{d2} = \exp \left[\frac{(L_5 p'_1 + L_6) - (L p_1 + L_6)}{(L_1 p'_1 + L_2) + (L_5 p_1 + L_6)} \right]^{n_1} \exp \left[\frac{(L_7 p'_2 + L_6) - (L_7 P_2 + L_8)}{(L_7 p'_2 + L_2) + (L_7 P_2 + L_8)} \right]^{n_2}$$

where h_i ($i = 0, 1, 2$) denotes the constants used for reducing the bias in the class of estimators, H denotes the set of those estimators that can be constructed from t_{di} ($i = 0, 1, 2$) and $\mathbf{R}$

denotes the set of real numbers (for detail see Singh et. al. (2008)). Also, $L_i (i=1,2,\dots,8)$ are either real numbers or the functions of the known parameters of the auxiliary attributes.

Expressing t_{pd} in terms of e 's, we have

$$t_p = \bar{Y}(1+e_0) \left[h_0 + h_1(1+\varphi_1 e'_1)^{m_1} (1+\varphi_1 e_1)^{-m_1} (1+\varphi_2 e'_2)^{-m_2} \right. \\ \left. + h_2 \exp(\theta_1 [e'_1 - e_1] [1 + \theta_1 (e'_1 - e_1)]^{-1})^{n_1} \exp(\theta_2 e'_2 [1 + \theta_2 e'_2]^{n_2}) \right] \quad (6.3)$$

After expanding, subtracting $\bar{Y}$ from both sides of the equation (6.3) and neglecting the terms having power greater than two, we have

$$(t_{pd} - \bar{Y}) = \bar{Y} [e_0 + h_1(m_1 \varphi_1 e'_1 - m_1 \varphi_1 e_1 - m_2 \varphi_2 e'_2) + h_2(n_1 \theta_1 e'_1 - n_1 \theta_1 e_1 + n_2 \theta_2 e'_2)] \quad (6.4)$$

Squaring both sides of (6.4) and then taking expectations, we get MSE of the estimator t_p up to the first order of approximation, as

$$MSE(t_{pd}) = \bar{Y}^2 [h_1^2 R_1 + h_2^2 R_2 + 2h_1 h_2 R_3 + 2h_1 R_4 + 2h_2 R_5] \quad (6.5)$$

$$\text{where, } \left. \begin{aligned} h_1 &= \frac{R_2 R_4 - R_3 R_5}{R_1 R_2 - R_3^2} \\ h_2 &= \frac{R_1 R_5 - R_3 R_4}{R_1 R_2 - R_3^2} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6.6)$$

and

$$\left. \begin{aligned} R_1 &= \varphi_1^2 m_1^2 f_3 C_{p_1}^2 + \varphi_2^2 m_2^2 f_2 C_{p_2}^2 \\ R_2 &= \theta_1^2 n_1^2 f_3 C_{p_1}^2 + \theta_2^2 n_2^2 f_2 C_{p_2}^2 \\ R_3 &= m_2 n_2 f_2 \varphi_2 \theta_2 C_{p_2}^2 - n_1 m_1 \varphi_1 \theta_1 f_2 k_\varphi C_{p_1}^2 \\ R_4 &= -m_1 \varphi_1 f_3 k_{pb_1} C_{p_1}^2 - m_2 \varphi_2 f_2 k_{pb_2} C_{p_2}^2 \\ R_5 &= -n_1 \theta_1 f_3 k_{pb_1} C_{p_1}^2 + n_2 \theta_2 f_2 k_{pb_2} C_{p_2}^2 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6.7)$$

Data: (Source: Singh and Chaudhary (1986), p. 177).

The population consists of 34 wheat farms in 34 villages in certain region of India. The variables are defined as:

y = area under wheat crop (in acres) during 1974.

p_1 = proportion of farms under wheat crop which have more than 500 acres land during 1971.

and

p_2 = proportion of farms under wheat crop which have more than 100 acres land during 1973.

For this data, we have

$$N=34, \bar{Y}=199.4, P_1=0.6765, P_2=0.7353, S_y^2=22564.6, S_{\phi_1}^2=0.225490, S_{\phi_2}^2=0.200535,$$

$$\rho_{pb_1}=0.599, \rho_{pb_2}=0.559, \rho_{\phi}=0.725.$$

Table 6.1: PRE of different estimators of $\bar{Y}$ with respect to $\bar{y}$

CHOICE OF SCALERS, when $h_0 = 0$ $h_1 = 1$ $h_2 = 0$						
m_1	m_2	L_1	L_2	L_3	L_4	PRE'S
0	1			1	0	108.16
1	0	1	0			121.59
1	1	1	1	1	1	142.19
1	1	1	0	1	0	133.40
1	1	C_{p_1}	ρ_{pb_1}	C_{p_2}	ρ_{pb_2}	144.78
1	1	NP_1	K_{pb_1}	NP_2	K_{pb_2}	136.90
1	1	NP_1	f	NP_2	f	133.30
1	1	N	K_{pb_1}	N	K_{pb_2}	135.73
1	1	NP_1	P_1	NP_2	P_2	137.09
1	1	n	P_1	n	P_2	138.23
1	1	N	ρ_{pb_1}	N	ρ_{pb_2}	135.49
1	1	n	P_1	n	P_2	138.97
1	1	N	P_1	N	P_2	135.86
When, $h_0 = 0$ $h_1 = 0$ $h_2 = 1$						
n_1	n_2	L_5	L_6	L_7	L_8	PRE'S
1	0	1	0	1	0	130.89
0	-1	1	0	1	0	108.93
1	-1	1	0	1	0	146.63
1	-1	1	1	1	1	121.68
1	-1	1	1	1	0	127.24
1	-1	C_{p_1}	ρ_{pb_1}	C_{p_2}	ρ_{pb_2}	123.43
1	-1	NP_1	K_{pb_1}	NP_2	K_{pb_2}	145.49
1	-1	NP_1	f	NP_2	f	146.57
1	-1	N	K_{pb_1}	N	K_{pb_2}	145.84
1	-1	NP_1	P_1	NP_2	P_2	145.43
1	-1	n	P_1	n	P_2	145.03

1	-1	N	ρ_{pb_1}	N	ρ_{pb_2}	145.92
1	-1	n	P_1	n	P_2	144.85
1	-1	N	P_1	N	P_2	145.80
When, $h_0 = 0$ $h_1 = 0$ $h_2 = 1$ also $L_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, 8) = 1$ $m_1 = m_2 = n_1 = n_2 = 1$						PRE(t_{pd})=154.28

7. Conclusion

In this paper, we have suggested a class of estimators in single and two-phase sampling by using point bi serial correlation and phi correlation coefficient. From Table 4.1 and Table 6.1, we observe that the proposed estimator t_p and t_{pd} performs better than other estimators considered in this paper.

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